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Analysis of the Causes of Human Trafficking In East Nusa Tenggara Province

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Abstract

The aims of this study are to determine the main factors causing the occurrence of human trafficking in NTT and to build a model of the causes of human trafficking. This research is a survey research with the population is a victim of human trafficking in the East Nusa Tenggara Province. The sample was 49 victims of human trafficking from Timor Tengah Selatan (TTS) and Belu districts who were selected by purposive sampling. The instrument used was a questionnaire using an ordinal measurement scale (Likert scale) which contained 37 questions as well as research variables (attributes). Data were analyzed using factor analysis. The results of the study showed that of the 37 variables, 7 factors are formed. There are economic and cultural factors, employment and income opportunities, early-age marriage, education, poverty, limited access to information, and quick rich desires. Economic and cultural factors are the main causes of human trafficking in NTT Province. The equation model produced for each factor are $F_1 = X_3 + X_4 + X_5 + X_9 + 0.696X_{13} + 0.714X_{14} + 0.505X_{25}$; $F_2 = 0.783X_{18} + 0.618X_{19} + 0.555X_{20} + 0.633X_{22} + 0.603X_{23} + 0.625X_{24} + 0.598X_{26}$; $F_3 = 0.607X_{12} + 0.700X_{27} + 0.848X_{28} + 0.798X_{29} + 0.595X_{30} + 0.629X_{32}$; $F_4 = 0.524X_{11} + 0.743X_{15} + 0.866X_{16} + 0.567X_{17}$; $F_5 = 0.658X_6 + 0.833X_7 + 0.750X_{10}$; $F_6 = 0.850X_1 + 0.826X_2 + 0.706X_{21}$ dan $F_7 = 0.793X_8$.

Keywords: Human Trafficking, Nusa Tenggara Timur

1. INTRODUCTION

The human trafficking phenomenon never stops. Lately, human trafficking has flourished with various modus operandi. The International Labor Organization (ILO) estimates that 20.9 million people work as slaves and 1.2 million children are sold every year. Indonesia is one of the main sources of trafficking.

East Nusa Tenggara Province is one of the provinces located in the eastern part of Indonesia. This province is known as the kitchen of human trafficking. Based on data from the Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Agency in NTT Province, the number of human trafficking cases is almost evenly distributed in 22 districts. The NTT Regional Police affirmed that out of 2,279 victims of human trafficking that departed from 2015 to 31 July 2016, there were 451 people identified as being related to handling human trafficking cases by the NTT Regional Police [1]. From these cases, there are various forms of violence such as physical, psychological, sexual violence, neglect, exploitation, and others.

The low level of education and the need for money are factors that cause victims to be recruited, sold, moved and resold. Human trafficking raises various crimes such as fraud, violence, and exploitation, and deprived of human rights. These crimes cause suffering and prolonged trauma.

This problem raises a sense of concern and discomfort from various parties. The NTT Provincial Government feels disturbed when there is a new title for NTT, namely NTT emergency trafficking. This is because the problem of human trafficking is referred to as a legal and humanitarian problem. Therefore, this problem is often handled by a legal approach [2]

Human Trafficking is defined as the recruitment, transportation, transfer or reception of people using threats or the use of violence and other forms of coercion, kidnapping, fraud, vulnerable positions by giving or receiving payments to reach agreement from people who have control over others for the purpose of exploitation. The same thing is confirmed by [3]. Human trafficking is a developing criminal activity that involves the movement of victims with violence or coercion for sexual exploitation or labor. Another opinion said that human trafficking is often facilitated without being realized by the tourism business [4].

Human trafficking, forced labor, and slavery have become important issues in the current era. However, the efforts to reject and prevent this problem received strong criticism [5]. Many cases that occur originated from fraud committed by family, friends or neighbors who actually must be able to protect. The global crisis of human trafficking involves the exploitation of people for personal gain and affects millions of people [6]. The human trafficking network is a network that is difficult to decide because it involves groups or individuals who are difficult to touch by law. Human trafficking, including the trade in sex and labor, is a global problem affecting 20.9 million people worldwide. The National Human Trafficking Hotline identified 36,270 cases of human trafficking in the United States since 2007 [7].

Throughout history, cases of human trafficking have been very difficult to identify and resolve. This case involves an experienced syndicate so that it is difficult to trace in ordinary ways. Therefore to handle this case must begin with finding the root of the problem.

The following cultural factors contribute to the occurrence of human trafficking, namely the role of women in the family, the role of children in the family, early marriage, and the history of employment due to debt [8]. Human trafficking in NTT Province has become a significant social problem. This case has caused public unrest in general and prolonged trauma for victims. More than that, this case has resulted in ever-increasing casualties.

As far as the researcher observes, there have been no studies related to the causes of human trafficking in NTT. The handling of human trafficking cases has not been carried out optimally because it does not yet know the root of the problem. Therefore this study aims to determine the factors that cause human trafficking. This effort is carried out to overcome the problem of human trafficking and intervene according to the goals and objectives.

Allegedly the base causes of human trafficking are economic transition and poverty. In addition, it was made worse by the lack of implementation of national and regional policies in overcoming this problem. Various efforts have been made by the government, but have not yet achieved optimal results. In fact, the data notes that the higher the number of human trafficking cases in NTT. The high number of cases of human trafficking has caused deep unrest for the people of NTT especially the rural communities. They feel uncomfortable and anxious about finding jobs that can bring money. Life anxiety for those who are forced to allow family members to find work outside the village/village can make them not optimal at work.

In addition, the handling of human trafficking cases that are complicated and incomplete has its own impact on society. The people of NTT as a community bordering on Timor Leste lost their trust in the government about their right to life. People feel that they are not protected by the government.

Based on the explanation of the background problem above, the research question are (1) What are the main factors causing the occurrence of human trafficking in NTT and (2) how is the model of the causes of human trafficking?

2. METHOD

This research is a survey research. The population of this study is a victim of human trafficking in East Nusa Tenggara Province. The sample of the study was the victims of 49 people who were selected by purposive sampling. 49 people came from two districts in NTT, and there are Timor Tengah Selatan (TTS) and Belu.

The instrument used was a questionnaire using an ordinal measurement scale (Likert scale). The questionnaire contains 37 questions which are also research variables (attributes). The 37 questions outlined in 12 aspects of the causes of human trafficking, namely poverty, lack of awareness / understanding, rich desire, culture, lack of education, lack of employment opportunities, lack of access to information about employment risks, economics, early marriage, migration, law and law, and law enforcement. Each question is rated 1 to 5, each of which strongly disagrees, disagrees, simply agrees, agrees and strongly agrees. Data were analyzed using the Factor Analysis method, which is one of the multivariate statistical methods that explain the relationship between variables that are mutually independent of one another. Based on this method one or more sets of variables are obtained that are less than the initial variable called Factor [9].

The instrument of this study is a questionnaire using an ordinal measurement scale containing 37 questions as well as research variables (attributes). Each question is rated 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Instruments are prepared based on 12 aspects of human trafficking, namely poverty, lack of awareness/understanding, rich desire, culture, lack of education, lack of employment opportunities, lack of access to information about employment risks, economics, early marriage, migration, law and rule, and enforcement. Law. Data were analyzed using factor analysis.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Communal value is the proportion of the initial variable variance that can be explained by existing factors. The greater the value of communality indicates the greater relationship between variables and factors. Based on the value of Measure Sampling Adequacy (MSA) of 37 variables, there are only 31 variables that are feasible to be analyzed using factor analysis. Table 1 describes communal values for 37 variables.

Table 1. Communal Values

Variable	Initial	Extraction	Variable	Initial	Extraction
X1	1.000	0.842	X17	1.000	0.763
X2	1.000	0.837	X18	1.000	0.698
X3	1.000	0.669	X19	1.000	0.764
X4	1.000	0.673	X20	1.000	0.692
X5	1.000	0.691	X21	1.000	0.688
X6	1.000	0.810	X22	1.000	0.833
X7	1.000	0.897	X23	1.000	0.820
X8	1.000	0.763	X24	1.000	0.845
X9	1.000	0.695	X25	1.000	0.735
X10	1.000	0.767	X26	1.000	0.804
X11	1.000	0.656	X27	1.000	0.620
X12	1.000	0.778	X28	1.000	0.839
X13	1.000	0.727	X29	1.000	0.842
X14	1.000	0.692	X30	1.000	0.676
X15	1.000	0.768	X32	1.000	0.635
X16	1.000	0.893			

The values in Table 1 show the ability of the factors formed in explaining the variance of the origin variable. The biggest value is owned by the X7 variable which is equal to 0.897. This means that 89.7% of the variance of variable X7 can be explained by the factors formed. While the smallest value is owned by the variable X27 which is equal to 0.620. The greater the communal value of a variable indicates the more closely related to the factors formed.

Factoring is a core process in factor analysis. Extracting existing variables to form one or more factors that contain a number of variables. In this study, the extraction process is to estimate the weight of the factor using Principal Component Analysis. In the main component method, the criteria for determining the number of factors that can be formed can be seen from variables that have eigenvalues $\lambda_i \geq 1$. There are 31 variables included in factor analysis. Based on Table 2, it is known that the first factor has an eigenvalue of 11.602 with a variance of 37.425%. The second-factor eigenvalues 2.939 with a variance of 9,482%, the 3rd-factor eigenvalues 2,570 with variance 8,289% and so on until the 31st factor with eigenvalue 0.02 and variance 0.063%.

Table 2 Result of Extracting

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.602	37.425	37.425	11.602	37.425	37.425	4.115	13.275	13.275
2	2.939	9.482	46.907	2.939	9.482	46.907	3.998	12.896	26.171
3	2.570	8.289	55.196	2.570	8.289	55.196	3.965	12.790	38.961
4	2.171	7.004	62.200	2.171	7.004	62.200	3.154	10.174	49.135
5	1.501	4.840	67.040	1.501	4.840	67.040	3.090	9.969	59.105
6	1.411	4.551	71.592	1.411	4.551	71.592	3.027	9.764	68.869
7	1.217	3.927	75.519	1.217	3.927	75.519	2.061	6.650	75.519
8	0.947	3.055	78.574						
9	0.827	2.669	81.243						
10	0.786	2.536	83.779						
11	0.745	2.403	86.182						
12	0.607	1.957	88.139						
13	0.571	1.842	89.982						
14	0.453	1.460	91.441						
15	0.383	1.237	92.678						
16	0.356	1.147	93.825						
17	0.311	1.003	94.829						
18	0.268	0.865	95.693						
19	0.262	0.847	96.540						
20	0.201	0.648	97.188						
21	0.145	0.467	97.655						
22	0.139	0.447	98.102						
23	0.119	0.383	98.485						
24	0.110	0.355	98.840						
25	0.093	0.302	99.142						
26	0.073	0.235	99.377						
27	0.056	0.181	99.557						
28	0.046	0.148	99.705						
29	0.042	0.134	99.839						
30	0.030	0.098	99.937						
31	0.020	0.063	100.000						

Table 2 shows that there are seven factors that have eigenvalues greater than one and have a cumulative value of 75.519%. This result shows that there are only 7 factors that explain the 31 initial variables. This means that the seven factors can explain the total variability of 31 initial variables at 75,519% without reducing the initial information of all these variables. The remaining 24,481% is explained by other factors not examined. To facilitate the interpretation of factors, factor rotation will be carried out. Table 3 shows the weight of the factor after rotating or the correlation coefficient between the X_i variables with each factor.

Table 3. Factor loading (factor weight)

Variable	Komponent						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
X1	0.200	-0.081	0.064	0.104	0.162	0.850	0.178
X2	0.168	0.161	0.099	-0.079	0.258	0.826	0.136
X3	0.674	0.077	0.116	0.126	0.211	0.358	0.083
X4	0.505	0.099	-0.238	0.458	0.218	0.294	0.090
X5	0.573	0.259	-0.103	-0.004	0.223	0.328	0.357
X6	0.372	-0.096	-0.064	0.275	0.658	0.240	0.302
X7	0.281	0.139	0.131	0.199	0.833	0.103	0.194
X8	0.214	-0.024	0.198	0.020	0.200	0.090	0.793
X9	0.612	0.194	0.196	-0.117	0.392	-0.019	0.277
X10	0.233	0.238	0.224	0.127	0.750	0.164	0.002
X11	0.410	0.049	0.202	0.524	0.358	0.127	0.159
X12	0.284	0.067	0.607	0.081	0.170	0.219	0.491
X13	0.696	-0.064	0.403	0.222	0.101	-0.094	0.086
X14	0.714	0.208	0.122	0.192	0.135	0.261	-0.008
X15	0.251	0.207	0.137	0.743	0.272	0.133	0.001
X16	0.176	0.321	0.038	0.866	0.029	0.048	-0.064
X17	-0.084	0.515	0.301	0.567	0.222	0.099	0.144
X18	0.094	0.783	0.133	0.155	0.065	0.154	0.072
X19	-0.025	0.618	0.163	0.209	0.372	0.415	0.026
X20	0.007	0.555	0.306	0.241	0.060	-0.029	0.477
X21	0.017	0.216	0.244	0.232	-0.064	0.706	-0.157
X22	0.215	0.633	0.030	0.232	-0.253	0.467	-0.224
X23	0.339	0.603	0.348	0.073	0.447	0.029	-0.116
X24	0.517	0.625	0.196	0.128	0.292	0.015	-0.217
X25	0.505	0.443	0.239	0.301	0.349	-0.045	-0.111
X26	0.452	0.598	0.110	0.283	0.001	-0.205	0.327
X27	0.123	0.024	0.700	-0.273	0.040	0.033	0.191
X28	0.056	0.197	0.848	0.099	0.155	0.173	0.118
X29	0.119	0.347	0.798	0.222	0.103	0.097	0.033
X30	-0.006	0.267	0.595	0.425	0.037	0.163	0.207
X32	0.204	0.061	0.629	0.189	0.072	-0.008	-0.390

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that 0.850 is the correlation coefficient value between the variables X1 and the sixth factor. This value is the highest value of the correlation coefficient between X1 and the existing factors. This shows that the X1 variable is included as a member of the 6th-factor component. For X2 variables, it can be seen that the highest correlation coefficient is in factor 6 which is 0.826. This value indicates that X2 is a member of the 6th factor. Analog with variables X1 and X2, for other variables that can be determined is part of which factor.

Factor 1 consists of variables X3, X4, X5, X9, X13, X14, and X25. This factor 1 is called economic and cultural factors. Because the value of the correlation (factor weight) of all positive variables means that the greater the responsibility of respondents to the family, the more it makes respondents interested in becoming migrant workers

in this case as victims of human trafficking. Women are considered easy to make money in the family. A big responsibility in supporting a family that needs money is the trigger for human trafficking.

Factor 2 consists of variables X18, X19, X20, X22, X23, X24, and X26. Factor 2 is called the factor of employment and income. Correlation values of all positive variables indicate that the more difficult respondents get decent jobs, the more making respondents interested in becoming migrant workers in this case as victims of human trafficking. An educational background that only completes elementary, middle or high school makes it difficult for them to get a decent job. This condition makes the victims accept any work offered that it is important to get money.

Factor 3 consists of variables X12, X27, X28, X29, X30, and X32. This factor 3 is called the factor of early marriage. Because the value of the correlation (factor weight) of all variables is positive, the younger the age of the respondent at marriage makes the respondent more interested in becoming a migrant worker in this case as a victim of human trafficking. In the family of girls, it is often a burden on the family economy so that one way to reduce the burden is to marry her off at an early age. Early marriage has the potential to cause a failure of marriage which leads to difficulties in supporting themselves and their children. This was revealed in an interview with Dahlia. *I married at the age of 14 years and have 4 children. I have been single parents since my youngest child was 3 years old. I decided to become a migrant worker because I wanted to give a good future for children. It turned out that I was cheated and not paid for working for 2 years. My children I entrusted to my family suffered.*

Factor 4 consists of variables X11, X15, X16, and X17. Factor 4 is called the factor of low education. The value of the correlation (factor weight) of all positive variables indicates that the lower the level of education of the respondent the more interested in becoming a migrant worker in this case as a victim of human trafficking. Most victims of human trafficking are those with elementary or junior high school education and some even drop out of school. The low level of education has resulted in the limitations of thinking so that it is easily influenced and deceived.

Factor 5 consists of variables X6, X7, and X10. This factor is called the poverty factor. All variables have positive correlation values. This condition shows that the more respondents have many needs, the more interested in becoming migrant workers in this case as victims of human trafficking. Poverty has forced many families to plan life support strategies. One strategy taken is to migrate to work whatever is important to get money. This was illustrated by YS in an interview that he chose to become a female laborer when the family's economic situation was very bad. She has seven children, while the husband does not have a job. She was arrested by Malaysian police while crossing from Nunukan and deported. Thus he said, *"I was forced to become a migrant worker, to free my children from poverty."*

Factor 6 consists of variables X1, X2, and X21. This factor 6 is called the factor Lack of access to information. The correlation value for all variables is positive. This shows that the less knowledge the respondent has about employment abroad, the greater the desire to become a migrant worker. Most people victims of human trafficking do not realize or know that there is a danger of trafficking. This means that they do not know of fraudulent ways to trap them in slavery-like jobs. The number of people who do not know the dangers of the work involved. They are only oriented to income or income received.

Factor 7 only consists of variable X8. Factor 4 is called the rich quick desire factor. All variables are positive, and the more respondents have many needs, the more interested in becoming migrant workers in this case as victims of human trafficking. The desire to have material and a higher standard of living triggers human trafficking. Life that is not feasible and squeezed by debt makes some people want to be rich.

This was revealed in an interview with MT which we quoted as follows: *"I and my sister-in-law are convinced that working in Malaysia is not difficult, the salary is large, and there is no need to bring clothes."* Women's human longing for a decent life made him not think long about the strength of the recruiters' false promises. A 13-year-old female victim told her that *"at that time I was promised a high salary abroad to make me run away from*

home. In Malaysia, I worked from 05.00 to 23.00 local time. When I was sick, I was transported and dumped on the beach. I worked for three years without being paid.

From the seven factors obtained, it can be seen that the first factor (economy and culture) is the main cause of human trafficking cases because these factors have eigenvalues and the largest percentage of variance is 11.602 and 37.425%.

The equation model produced for each factor is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_1 &= X_3 + X_4 + X_5 + X_9 + 0.696X_{13} + 0.714X_{14} + 0.505X_{25} \\
 F_2 &= 0.783X_{18} + 0.618X_{19} + 0.555X_{20} + 0.633X_{22} + 0.603X_{23} + 0.625X_{24} + 0.598X_{26} \\
 F_3 &= 0.607X_{12} + 0.700X_{27} + 0.848X_{28} + 0.798X_{29} + 0.595X_{30} + 0.629X_{32} \\
 F_4 &= 0.524X_{11} + 0.743X_{15} + 0.866X_{16} + 0.567X_{17} \\
 F_5 &= 0.658X_6 + 0.833X_7 + 0.750X_{10} \\
 F_6 &= 0.850X_1 + 0.826X_2 + 0.706X_{21} \\
 F_7 &= 0.793X_8
 \end{aligned}$$

The seven models produced will be more useful if used for further analysis by calculating the score of each factor based on the variables contained in each factor.

4. CONCLUSION

Referring to research results and discussions in the previous section, a conclusion is drawn as follows: (1) Factors that influence the occurrence of economic and cultural human trafficking, employment and income opportunities, early marriage, low education, poverty, lack of access to information, and the desire to get rich quick; (2) The dominant factor that causes human trafficking is Factor 1, namely economy and culture with a variance percentage of 37.425%; (3) The model for each factor are $F_1 = X_3 + X_4 + X_5 + X_9 + 0.696X_{13} + 0.714X_{14} + 0.505X_{25}$, $F_2 = 0.783X_{18} + 0.618X_{19} + 0.555X_{20} + 0.633X_{22} + 0.603X_{23} + 0.625X_{24} + 0.598X_{26}$, $F_3 = 0.607X_{12} + 0.700X_{27} + 0.848X_{28} + 0.798X_{29} + 0.595X_{30} + 0.629X_{32}$, $F_4 = 0.524X_{11} + 0.743X_{15} + 0.866X_{16} + 0.567X_{17}$, $F_5 = 0.658X_6 + 0.833X_7 + 0.750X_{10}$, $F_6 = 0.850X_1 + 0.826X_2 + 0.706X_{21}$, and $F_7 = 0.793X_8$.

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